

Plug-in Hybrid Electric Buses Total Cost of Ownership Optimization at Fleet Level based on Battery Aging

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Abstract

In this paper a hierarchical energy management strategy design methodology for total cost of ownership management at fleet level is proposed. The decisions are taken from the fleet level point of view, to optimize the whole fleet based on the hierarchical decision maker and management, composed of three levels. The outer part is the offline route-to-bus data exploitation and decision maker, aiming to establish the dynamic programming optimization design. The next level is the offline optimization bus-to-route. Based on the previous decision, the neuro-fuzzy learns from the global optimal solutions. Finally, the trained fuzzy-logic strategy is used to manage the online operation. This fleet is re-organized and the online operation energy management strategy is updated throughout the bus lifetime. These decisions are made based on the evaluated battery lifetime of the fleet, with the aim to meet the planned total cost of ownership requirements. The total cost of ownership for the bus-to-route energy management strategy, has been improved a 7.65 % at fleet level against a charge-sustaining charge-depleting strategy. In the route-to-bus fleet re-organization and update, up to 5.51 % total cost of ownership improvement at fleet level has been obtained against not applying the fleet management.

Keywords— Plug-in hybrid electric electric buses (PHEBs), total cost of ownership, hierarchical energy management strategy, battery degradation, neuro-fuzzy, digitalization

1 Introduction

The growing concern in regard to greenhouse gas emissions issue has derived on a mind shift in the automotive industry, looking for more sustainable and greener solutions. The transport decarbonization challenge is seen to be spearheaded by public transport, owing to the favorable driving characteristics [1]. As a result, several studies have been performed on the subject of analyzing the available alternative technologies, pointing out hybrid electric buses (HEBs) and full electric buses as the most viable options [2, 3, 4].

Among the available alternative technologies, HEBs are found as the intermediate step between conventional and battery electric buses (BEBs), having the closest manufacturing costs to conventional diesel buses and offering improved energy efficiencies [2, 3, 4, 5]. However, due to the reduced energy storage system and the resulting constrained use of it, HEBs show similar polluting behavior to conventional buses regarding the environmental footprint [5]. Setting the target for the full decarbonization of urban road transport, it has to be addressed with the deployment of the available full electric buses solutions.

The lithium-ion batteries (BTs) price decrease (price drop of around 79% since 2010 [6]) have placed BEBs as the widespread solution [3, 4], in regard to full electric buses. However, to reach the zero-emissions of public transport target, wider range of solutions are required in order to meet the most demanding and longer routes requirements [7, 8]. In this respect, fuel cell hybrid electric buses (FCHEBs) are suitable solutions for covering these kind of routes. The main drawback of FCHEBs, is still the lack of hydrogen refueling stations and the high price of the fuel cells.

The closest solution to FCHEBs and the main competitors of full electric buses, due to the technical characteristics and lower manufacturing cost, are plug-in hybrid electric buses (PHEBs) [9, 10, 11]. The larger BT capacities than HEBs and additional flexibility degree of charging, allow to harness the BT utilization, increasing the zero emission zone range. In addition, the advances in PHEBs will pave the way for the oncoming FCHEBs implementation, as the topologies and degrees of freedom are similar,

being the developed energy management strategies (EMSs) for PHEBs directly applicable on FCHEBs [12, 13].

All the aforementioned powertrains have in common the higher investment costs beside conventional diesel buses, making the integration of alternative solutions a challenging process. On the pro side, the lower operational costs of PHEBs and BEBs, together with the high yearly driven distances, help to compensate the manufacturing extra costs [1, 4, 5, 14], still not being the case for the FCHEBs. In order to evaluate the costs offset, total cost of ownership (TCO) calculation plays a key role on the transport electrification process [4, 7].

The TCO calculation is determined with fixed conditions, which vary throughout the bus lifetime and generate uncertainties on the TCO, as it has been evidenced in the literature [7, 15, 16]. The main reason to this fact is the high sensitivity of the TCO to the operational aspect [4, 7, 16]. A technical proposal is the continuous monitoring of the vehicles operation, by means of the new opportunities of digitalization. Indeed, this monitoring allows to have the fleet overall view, having an additional degree of freedom and point of view to process, analyze and make decisions, with the aim of managing and further improving the overall fleet TCO.

Digitalization is the process of providing vehicles with sensors to acquire information, storing this information in the cloud data storage and analyzing the data [17]. This new trend enables to monitor the energetic operation of each vehicle from a local and fleet point of view. Consequently, the decision making for the fleet TCO management is carried out from an upper level of the whole fleet overview. Based on this decision, the lower level decision making for the EMS design of each bus is performed from the fleet and local points of view. The main challenge for the TCO management at fleet level and digitalization is the large data volume to be managed by fleet managers. Consequently, new automated and advanced tools are needed for the data analysis and decision making, becoming a thriving area of research [18, 19].

In [20] a methodology for improving the TCO by means of BT lifetime management at fleet level was carried out for PHEBs. With the aim to further improve the TCO of the whole fleet, an improved

intelligent and adaptive EMS developed in [21] has been integrated in the TCO management at fleet level based on the BT lifetime. It is noteworthy the additional learning speed improvement of the intelligent and adaptive EMS reducing from 5 to 3 the number of inputs. The inputs reduction has been carried out based on a variable correlation study, dismissing those variables with correlation. This merge allows to make decisions from the fleet overview and the life status of each bus, allowing to further improve the TCO.

1.1 Literature Review

PHEBs operation rely strongly on the suitable and efficient power/torque split among the available sources, as well as the FCHEBs. The complex energy division calculation is solved based on the EMS, focused on the maximization of the overall efficiency and minimization of the operation costs [19]. Consequently, the hybrid vehicles operation and the EMS are closely related [10].

Traditionally, the proposed EMSs in the literature have been classified as rule-based (RB) and optimization-based (OB) EMSs. On the one hand, RB EMSs are generally designed for specific driving cycles and operating conditions, having limited adaptability to the real changing conditions. On the other hand, despite the good results achieved with OB EMSs, the future driving conditions need to be known or predicted and commonly they require high computational efforts, making more difficult the online on-board implementation [9, 10, 19]. Therefore the effective design of an EMS is a complex task, since in real driving conditions the energy uncertainties and disruptions are tough to predict [10, 22].

Nowadays there is a new trend to provide vehicles with sensors, enabling to monitor the operation of each vehicle. This process is known as vehicles digitalization and lies on the data acquisition, data storage, computation and data analysis in the cloud [17, 19]. The cloud-based system allows to have "unlimited" resources, widening possibilities of optimizing the EMS through global methods [19]. In addition, by means of cloud-computing, historical operation data exploitation is a valuable input to provide enough information and further improve the EMS design [19, 23, 24]. As a result, learning based EMSs have

been emerged, learning from a data-base and gaining the ability to self-adapt to the changing real driving conditions [10].

In the literature, several learning based EMSs have been published. Khayyam et al. [25] proposed an EMS based on 3 fuzzy controls tuned based on a hybrid adaptive neural-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) genetic algorithm. Ozatay et al. [24] developed cloud based system, with the aim to fed back to the driver the optimized driving guidelines. A data-base with the optimal speed profile operation by means of dynamic programming (DP) was used to train neural networks and implement in the vehicle as EMS [26, 27]. In addition, Tian et al. improved this approach implementing two neuro-fuzzy systems, one for the target state of charge (SOC) and another for the genset output [11]. Yang2017 et al. [28] exploited the compiled information offline, with the aim to cluster 6 different driving behaviors and model them based on a Markov chain. The online part was based on a super vector machine, for identifying the recognized driving behaviors and applied the developed EMS for each driving behavior. Hu et al. [10] developed a deep reinforcement learning based EMS, learning from the torque and SOC operation.

The learning based EMS is a promising method, due to the high adaptability and the capability to learn from the historical data [10]. Furthermore, widening the scope from single vehicle level to the whole fleet will allow to learn from a more extend data-base and wider range of operation conditions. Regarding fleet management techniques, digitalization has enabled to offer new services [17]. The new provided services are oriented to energy savings, driving behavior, dynamic routing, charging schedule and diagnostics [12, 13, 17, 18]. In the literature several fleet management system approaches have been identified, with different purposes [9, 19]. Examining the proposed approaches, a classification based on the topics of each fleet management system approach has been done for a better understanding. The identified purposes are focused on the following areas: traffic jams avoidance [29, 30], vehicle diagnostics [31, 32], itinerary planning and charging regulation [33, 34] and scheduling [35, 36]. From the proposed approaches, in the literature there is a gap related to fleet management from an energetic point of view, with the aim to improve the TCO.

The wider range of conditions, will allow to learn from the changing conditions, improving the EMS adaptiveness to the driving disruptions. However, the majority of the existing literature aiming to improve the operation costs of PHEBs is mostly focused on fuel efficiency, limiting the BT lifetime [37, 38, 39]. Despite the BT prices have been decreased, they still have a great impact on the TCO [20, 39, 40]. BTs lifetime is shorter than power electronics lifetime and they have to be replaced with the aim to extend the bus optimum operation. These replacements are previously planned for the TCO determination and they have to be met. Therefore, aiming to minimize the operation costs as well as meeting the BT aging constrains, BT lifetime has to be managed, with the aim to optimize and further improve the TCO.

In the recent proposed approaches, BT aging management have gained importance in the EMS design. On the contrary, as it is stated in [39], the health conscious EMS design is still a challenging issue. Most of the researchers propose an initial EMS designed for the bus initial conditions with a set of boundaries. Throughout the bus lifetime, bus conditions vary and the BT state of health (SOH) is evaluated periodically. In this context, BT aging conscious EMS has to be updated and re-designed according to this new status [39]. In this regard, multi objective strategies have been proposed, such as the works proposed by Ma et al. and Herrera et al. [41, 42]. Based on genetic algorithms they tune the fuzzy-logic membership functions taking into account the BT degradation. Yue et al. [43], proposed a health conscious EMS update based on SOH decision-making. In this research the update and EMS re-optimization is done also based on GA. Other researchers have modeled the DP cost function with the aim to minimize the BT degradation. However, DP computation is heavy for the online implementation [39]. This is the reason that DP is mostly used for evaluation, comparison and analysis tool [39, 44, 45].

As it has been stated in Refs. [20, 39, 43], in a multi objective optimization, one target decision compromises the others. As a result, with the aim to optimize the TCO, decisions have to be made based on the TCO plan [20]. Currently, as it has been aforementioned intelligent and learning techniques for designing the EMS have increased their importance. These learning techniques facilitate the EMS design part, especially in the case study of a whole fleet, where all the buses have to be optimized in terms of

TCO, fuel efficiency and BT aging [21]. To fill the existing literature gap of an intelligent and adaptive BT aging conscious EMS at fleet level, a hierarchical decision maker and management to manage the TCO at fleet level is proposed in this paper.

1.2 Motivation and innovation

The purpose of this research work is to propose a TCO management methodology at fleet level, updating the EMS based on a hierarchical decision maker and management approach by means of the BT SOH at the evaluation point. The update of the decision-making process is based on the TCO plan, with the aim to further optimize it. A data-base of different DP operation optimizations with different auxiliary consumptions of the driving cycle route have been generated. For the EMS design, a neuro-fuzzy technique has been used for the rules and membership function intelligent tuning. Reducing the number of inputs from 5 to 3 of the neuro-fuzzy learning technique, it is noteworthy the training speed increase. In the previous approach the used 5 variables were power demand, speed, acceleration, state of charge and length ratio. Speed, acceleration and length ratio were correlated between them and therefore, using all these three variables just was increasing the computational time. Therefore, when these inputs for the neuro-fuzzy were eliminated, the training speed was considerably improved. One EMS has been designed for each route and afterwards it has been implemented online and evaluated. BT SOH evaluation point has been set, and with the obtained outcome of the SOH, decisions have been taken. For those buses with the BT SOH without deviations from the planned TCO, and EMS update has been carried out, as previously described. For those buses with the best and worst BT SOH, a route re-organization has been done, with the respective EMS update. This will help to fill the gap for developing intelligent and aging conscious EMS at fleet level, with the consequent fleet management. In addition, the development of TCO and EMS improvement intelligent techniques based on BT aging for PHEB will help to pave the way for the oncoming FCHEBs implementation.

1.3 Paper organization

The paper is organized as follows. First in Section 2 the bus technical characteristics and fleet routes are described. Section 3 presents the applied TCO model and the bus system and management descriptions are given. Afterwards in Section 4 the novelty of the paper is described, the methodology for optimizing the fleet TCO making decisions based on the aging of the BT. In Section 5 the obtained evaluation results are analyzed, and conclusions are given in Section 6.

2 Case Study

The analysis of this paper has been in reliance on the fleet described in Table 1. The fleet is composed of 10 series PHEBs, pulled by an electric motor powered by a BT pack and a genset, with the technical details shown in Table 1 and respective models overview presented in the next section with full details in [46, 42].

Table 1: Scenario approach [42].

Parameters		Parameters	
Fleet buses	10	Min./max. auxiliary consumption [kW]	12/18
Electric motor power [kW]	196.5	Lithium titanate oxide BT packs C-rate/energy [-/kWh]	8/24
Genset power [kW]	160	Opportunity charging power [kW]	150

Figure 1: Fleet routes speed profiles.

The urban routes have been generated from a data-base of standardized driving cycles and adapted to a bus driving behavior [47]. Each of the generated cycles of the fleet is shown in Fig. 1.

3 Model and methods

In this section a preliminary TCO calculation method, definition of the hierarchical decision maker and management, bus model and management and the utilized techniques are briefly introduced. First, the utilized TCO calculation model is described, with the definition of respective manageable factors for the TCO optimization. The hierarchical management outlook and the composing levels are described

from the inner to the outer level. Therefore first the online bus system model and management level is described. After this, the optimization and strategy design level is described with a brief overview of DP optimization and neuro-fuzzy learning techniques. This hierarchical decision maker and management is applied on the fleet TCO management methodology, described in the next section.

3.1 Total Cost of Ownership Calculation

Both the FEB and HEB have higher investment costs than conventional buses. However as it has been aforementioned, the high yearly driven distances of buses and the lower operational costs help to compensate the BT and manufacturing extra costs [1, 4, 5, 14]. The solution feasibility study has to be determined based on the calculation of the TCO, as it is the economic performance indicator, which includes investment cost, insurance, infrastructure, maintenance, driver, operation, carbon-taxes and end-of-life (EOL) [7, 46, 48].

From the above-mentioned factors forming the TCO, two different groups have been differentiated from the energetic manageability point of view: fixed and manageable costs. Figure 2 shows both groups of factors. Once the bus is under operational conditions, on the one hand, investment-cost, insurance, infrastructure, maintenance and driver costs have been taken as constant, since they cannot be managed from an energetic point of view. On the other hand, operation costs can be managed with direct impact on the respectively carbon taxes. As shown in Figure 2, the previously analyzed degrees of freedom regarding the PHEB controllability are the fuel consumption, charging cost and energy storage system utilization and consequent number of replacements.

Going deeper into the proposed TCO management techniques, two techniques have been differentiated. *Bus-to-route* approach lies on a short term improvement for fulfilling the efficiency goals of fuel consumption minimization. This optimization is carried out with the aim to optimize the bus according to the route. Once the bus has been operated for a defined period of time, operation data will be available and initial bus conditions vary. At this point the *route-to-bus* long-term improvement takes place. The

Figure 2: Total cost of ownership fixed and manageable costs based on the degrees of freedom from the energetic manageability point of view.

compiled historical data is exploited, with the aim to improve the optimization process. In addition bus conditions are updated and according to the new SOH of the BTs and TCO planning, decisions are taken. These decisions aimed to fix the operation to the TCO plan and can imply a fleet re-organization or EMS update for reducing the fuel consumption or reducing the BT utilization.

The TCO calculation has been carried out based on the aforementioned manageable costs, developing the following equation 1 [4, 14],

$$TCO = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(f_{ICE} \cdot C_{fuel/t} \cdot Dev_{fuel} + E_{cha} \cdot C_{kWh/t}) \cdot Op_{year} + C_{kW/t} \cdot P_{cha} + C_{BT} \cdot E_{BT} \cdot DR_{BT/t}}{(1 + dr)^T} \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{lifetime}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where T is the scenario duration (*years*), t is the current year, $f_{ICE} \left[\frac{l}{day} \right]$ is the fuel consumption, $C_{fuel/t} \left[\frac{€}{l} \right]$ is the annual fuel price, $E_{cha}(k)[kWh/day]$ is energy absorbed from the grid, $C_{kWh/t} \left[\frac{€}{kWh} \right]$ the referential annual energy cost of the grid, $Op_{year} \left[\frac{day}{year} \right]$ yearly operation days, $C_{kW/t} \left[\frac{€}{kW/year} \right]$ is the annual cost of the power, $P_{cha}(k) [kW]$ is the power of the charger, $C_{BT} \left[\frac{€}{kWh} \right]$ is the BT initial price, $E_{BT}[kWh]$ is the BT energy, $DR_{BT/t} \left[\frac{\%}{year} \right]$ depreciation rate of the BT per year and $dr[\%]$ is the discount rate. In Table 2 the applied techno-economic parameters for the TCO calculation are shown

Table 2: Total cost of ownership parameters.

	Acronym	Value	Unit	Reference
Fuel cost	C_{fuel}	0.95	€/l	[52]
Diesel fuel price development	Dev_{fuel}	2.3	%/year	[52]
Energy electricity cost	C_{kWh}	0.139	€/kWh	[52]
Power electricity cost	C_{kW}	25.9	€/kW/year	[5]
Electricity price development	Dev_{Elect}	3.7	%/year	[52]
Yearly operation days	Op_{year}	330	€/kW/year	[51] and own estimation
Service life	T	12	year	[5]
BT low cost scenario	C_{BT}	700	€/kWh	[54]
BT medium cost scenario	C_{BT}	1000	€/kWh	[50, 46]
BT high cost scenario	C_{BT}	1500	€/kWh	[53]
BT depreciation rate	DR_{BT}/t	-20	% in 12 years	[49, 54] and own estimation
Discount rate	dr	2.2	%	[52]

[2, 5, 46, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54].

The BT aging and number of replacements have been evaluated based on a rainflow cycle counting algorithm and a "Wöhler" curve based method [46], shown in Fig. 3 and extracted from [55].

3.2 Hierarchical decision maker and management from the fleet to the bus

Before the whole fleet level TCO optimization methodology description, a hierarchical outlook from the inside out of the developed different levels of the hierarchical decision maker and management are described. The developed approach is shown in Fig. 4.

In the previous subsection the bus local level online operation and model have been described, however,

Figure 3: Lithium titanate oxide "Wöhler" curve extracted from [55].

above that level a hierarchical structure makes decisions acting on the online operation.

Figure 4: Hierarchical decision maker from fleet to the bus scheme.

Starting from the inner level, in here the *online operation* of each bus is carried out. This level is composed of the EMS and the PHEB. The aim of this level is to evaluate the EMS running onboard the bus. Each EMS implemented in each bus is designed according to the upper levels. Therefore, the taken decisions are directly evaluated at this level.

The EMS design construction is based on the *offline optimization and strategy design at vehicle level*. On the one hand, the design part is based on a neuro-fuzzy learning technique, which is used for automatically tuning and determining the rules of the online fuzzy-logic strategy. On the other hand, the optimization used for feeding the learning technique is a DP global optimization technique. Each bus operation is optimized from fuel consumption point of view according to each route. In this way, the online EMS is designed, with the aim to replicate the optimal operation for fuel consumption minimization. The design process therefore is automatized and once the approach has been developed, the design complexity is low.

Since the operation obtained from the DP optimization is used as a reference for the EMS design in terms of genset and BT split factor usage, the optimization modeling allows to design an EMS based on

the TCO and BT aging analysis. The decision for the optimization modeling is taken on the *offline data exploitation and decision making at fleet level*. This decision for the optimization modelig is made based on the outlook of the whole fleet and affects to the the inner levels. The compiled fleet operation data is processed and analyzed, and based on the current status of the fleet in terms of TCO and BT SOH, decisions are made for further improving the TCO.

3.2.1 Online operation level

In order to analyze the operation from the energetic point of view, a backward quasi-static simulation model of a series topology PHEB has been developed in MATLAB [46]. Fig. 5 shows the bus model and management flow diagram. As inputs, the driving profile information and external depot charge are identified. Applying the dynamic equations of the bus with the respective efficiencies of the different bus components, the energy flow is obtained. The suitable and efficient power split factor among the genset and BT is managed by the EMS. The applied EMS has been a fuzzy-logic technique with three inputs and one output.

Figure 5: Online operation level series topology PHEB model and management scheme

The inputs and output for dealing with the complex problem of the split factor determination are shown in Figure 5. The inputs are the instantaneous traction and auxiliary power demand, length ratio, and BT SOC. Regarding the length ratio input, it is a factor that determines in every moment the remaining distance in percentage of the round-trip, a very utilized resource in the literature [11, 27, 56].

Finally the genset power is defined as output. This decision consequently sets the BT power demand for fulfilling the required instantaneous power demand of the bus. The genset output decision is based on the above-mentioned inputs and a Sugeno fuzzy inference system with Gaussian fuzzy membership functions. This EMS has been applied, since it has been previously validated in [57] that this EMS is appropriate for online execution in a real implementation.

3.2.2 Offline optimization and strategy design at vehicle level

At this subsection the basics of the DP operation optimization and neuro-fuzzy learning techniques of the *offline optimization and strategy design at vehicle level* are introduced.

Dynamic programming operation optimization: DP global optimization has been used to determine buses optimal operation and performance for the fuel consumption minimization, using Bellman’s dynamic programming algorithm [58]. This approach has been commonly used as a baseline for benchmarking the proposed new EMSs for hybrid electric vehicles and for off-line optimization [19, 59]. The optimization problem is based on the following cost function (J):

$$J = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \Delta m_{f_{ICE}}(U(k)) \cdot (\Delta x_{ref} \cdot w_x) \cdot T_s \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta m_{f_{ICE}}(U(k))$ is the fuel mass consumption (determined by the torque power split factor U), Δx_{ref} is the SOC current difference from a reference SOC and w_x is the weight applied to the SOC difference factor. All the calculation are carried out at each time step ($T_s=1$ s), within the urban route length (N). The utilized dynamic system has been modeled with a single state variable, BT SOC, still maintaining the accuracy [60]. The implemented constraints are explained in the following lines:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x(0) = x_0 \\ x(0) = x_{final} \\ x(k_f) \in [x_{f,min}, x_{f,max}] \\ u(k_f) \in [u_{f,min}, u_{f,max}] \\ x(k) \in \chi(k) \subset \mathfrak{R}^n \\ u(k) \in \chi(k) \subset \mathfrak{R}^m \end{array} \right. \quad (3)$$

where $x(0)$ sets the initial SOC, $x(k_f)$ and $u(k_f)$ set the SOC and split factor boundary of the optimization and $x(k)$ and $u(k)$ constraint the SOC and split factor values to real values.

The split factor at the initial point is set from $U = [-1, 1]$. For the case of series configuration the power demand (P_{dem} [W]) is split, as shown in Eq. 4, this factor determines the power split between the BT power (P_{BT} [W]) and the GS power (P_{genset} [W]).

$$P_{dem}(i) = \begin{cases} P_{Genset}(i) = P_{dem}(i) \cdot (1 - U(i)) \\ P_{BT}(i) = P_{dem}(i) \cdot U(i) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Based on this equation, $U = 1$ defines full electric mode; $U < 1$ & $U > 0$ defines hybrid mode; $U = 1$ defines full ICE mode and $U = -1$ defines full ICE mode recharging the BT.

For the DP optimizations, since the proposed approach is focused on PHEBs, the initial SOC has been set equal for all the routes and the final SOC has been set equal for all the optimizations of each route. The final SOC has been designed based on the level of demand of the route, with the goal of recharging the BT for reaching the initial SOC within the recharging time. The recharging time t_{cha} has been determined according to the route distance, being the recharging time in seconds, 9 times the kilometers of each specific route (empirically obtained). This decision has been established with the aim to achieve a BT depletion among all the route and standardize the recharging time calculation for all the routes in the fleet. Once the recharging time is set the final SOC SOC_{final} is calculated as follows:

$$E_{cha} = P_{cha} \cdot 1000 \cdot \frac{t_{cha}}{3600} - P_{max_{aux}} \cdot 1000 \frac{t_{cha}}{3600} \quad (5)$$

where P_{cha} kW is the charging power and $P_{max_{aux}}$ kW is the maximum auxiliary consumption with the aim to calculate the energy to be charged E_{cha} kWh in the worst scenario.

The usable energy E_{usable} kWh in the BT is calculated based on the BT energy E_{BT} kWh, current BT SOH SOH [%], BT utilization constant γ_{BT} and initial SOC x_0 [%] as follows:

$$E_{usable} = \left(E_{BT} \cdot \frac{SOH_{BT}}{100} \cdot \gamma_{BT} \right) \cdot \frac{x_0}{100} \quad (6)$$

Finally, the maximum discharged energy in the BT is calculated with the difference of Eqs. 6 and 5 and with the current energy the final SOC x_{final} [%] is calculated as follows:

$$x_{final} = \frac{E_{usable} - E_{cha}}{E_{BT} \cdot \frac{SOH_{BT}}{100}} \cdot 100 \quad (7)$$

In addition, the following powertrain operation constraints have been defined in the bus model optimization:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} SOC_{min} \leq SOC(k) \leq SOC_{max} \\ I_{BT_{min}} \leq I_{BT}(k) \leq I_{BT_{max}} \\ T_{genset_{min}} \leq T_{genset}(k) \leq T_{genset_{max}}, \omega_{genset_{min}} \leq \omega_{genset}(k) \leq \omega_{genset_{max}} \\ T_{em_{min}} \leq T_{em}(k) \leq T_{em_{max}}, \omega_{em_{min}} \leq \omega_{em}(k) \leq \omega_{em_{max}} \end{array} \right. \quad (8)$$

where $SOC(k)$, $I_{BT}(k)$, $T_{genset}(k)$, $\omega_{genset}(k)$, $T_{em}(k)$ and $\omega_{em}(k)$ represent the battery SOC, battery current, genset torque, genset rotational speed, electric motor torque and electric motor rotational speed with each respective limits at each discrete state k .

Having this constraint and optimal operation data-bases have been built, for different auxiliary consumptions, comprised between the minimum and maximum auxiliary consumptions, 12 kW and 18 kW

respectively. The decision of optimizing the profile for different auxiliary consumptions was based on a previous study, where the conclusion was that the auxiliary power consumption was identified as a critical factor for buses management [61]. In this way, for each route a data-base with global optimal operations is built.

Neuro-fuzzy tuning: The training procedure has been carried out based on the ANFIS technique, following the intelligent decision maker process shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Intelligent Decision Maker.

In the data preparation stage, the previously built data-base is preprocessed. The data-base is composed of the determined ANFIS training inputs and output. From the previously developed work [21], the number of inference systems have been reduced from 5 to 3, having the SOC, length ratio and power demand as inputs and the genset power as the output for defining the split factor between the BT and genset. The inputs reduction has been carried out based on a variable correlation study, dismissing those variables with correlation. Each input and output of the described data-base is firstly normalized into the range of $[0, 1]$.

The normalized data-base is split into different stages, divided in accordance to the route distance ratio and the amount of data of each set. First approach is carried out with 10 % steps division. For having homogeneous data-sets, for those sets larger than the others the 10 % distance ratio is split into two 5 % step sets.

Once the data is processed, the ANFIS initial fuzzy-logic design has been generated based on subtractive-clustering technique of the datasets [62]. At this second stage, the initial membership function design, number of outputs and rules are defined.

At the neuro-fuzzy learning stage, the initial membership functions and rules are trained based on the ANFIS technique, with the aim to tune the membership functions and refine the proposed first rules. It is worth mentioning that from the obtained 7 optimal operations, 6 are used for training and 1 for testing the ANFIS.

ANFIS technique was developed by Jang and improved by Sugeno and Kang [63, 64]. This technique is used for learning from a data-base and tuning the fuzzy inference system [25]. In this work the aforementioned data-base has been used for the learning and tuning process. The utilized technique for the neuro-fuzzy tuning stage is a hybrid learning algorithm in conformity with back-propagation and least-squares-type methods, as shown in Fig. 7. The main reasons for using the hybrid method have been the training speed, the error avoidance with the support of the second algorithm and the smarter networks training against supervised learning [25].

Figure 7: ANFIS architecture.

The ANFIS architecture is composed of 5 layers. The nodes x , y and z in layer 1 represent the system inputs that are SOC, length ratio and power demand respectively and the node in layer 5 the system output genset power. As it has been above-mentioned, the number of inputs for the ANFIS system have been reduced from 5 to 3. This reduction speeds up the learning process, maintaining the accuracy level. The output of each layer is expressed in Eq. 9.

$$\begin{cases}
 O^1 = \mu_{A_i} = e^{-\left(\frac{x-a}{b}\right)^2}, & i = 1, 2, 3 \\
 O^2 = \omega_i = \mu_{A_i}(x) \cdot \mu_{B_i}(y) \cdot \mu_{C_i}(z), & i = 1, 2, 3 \\
 O^3 = \bar{\omega}_i = \frac{\omega_i}{\sum_{j=1}^3 \omega_j}, & i = 1, 2, 3 \\
 O^4 = \bar{\omega}_i f_i = \bar{\omega}_i (p_i x + q_i y + r_i z + m_i), & i = 1, 2, 3 \\
 O^5 = f = \sum_{j=1}^3 \bar{\omega}_j f_j = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^3 \omega_j f_j}{\sum_{j=1}^3 \omega_j}
 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Layer 1 $O^1 = \mu_{A_i}$ is an adaptive layer where the fuzzification process is carried out according to the chosen membership function type, in this case Gaussian functions. In Eq. 9 x is one of the input variables and $\{a, b\}$ are the parameters defining the bell-shaped node. Layer 2 $O^2 = \omega_i$ is a fixed layer where each

rule weight is determined multiplying each node by the input signals. Layer 3 $O_i^3 = \bar{\omega}_i$ is a fixed layer where each rule weight is normalized with the sum of all rules. Layer 4 $O_i^4 = \bar{\omega}_i f_i$ is an adaptive layer where p, q, r, m fuzzy set design parameters are determined. Layer 5 $O_i^5 = f$ is a fixed layer where the output is computed, also known as sugeno defuzzification process [63].

Finally from the intelligent decision maker, the designed sugeno type fuzzy-logic EMS is obtained.

4 Fleet Management Methodology

The main contribution of this paper lies on an approach for the management of a whole fleet, based on the hierarchical decision maker and management. This approach, as shown in Figure 8, is divided in several levels and stages.

From the hierarchical decision maker and management point of view, two offline levels and one on-line level are differentiated. The *online operation level* and *offline optimization and strategy design at vehicle level* have been described previously in subsections 3.2.1 and 3.2.2 respectively. The *offline data exploitation and decision making at fleet level* has been introduced in 3.2, however, the inside of this level is further explained in the following lines divided into different stages.

Stage 1: Bus-to-route design

In the first stage the fleet *bus-to-route* optimization is performed. This optimization is focused on the EMS design of each bus for each route with the objective of fuel consumption minimization and BT lifetime management. In stage 1.1 the expected urban route profiles are analyzed. At this point as it has been explained in 3.2.2 the final SOC of each route is determined, determining the γ_{BT} and $\Delta SOC_{ref} w_{SOC}$ as 1. Following this, in the stage 1.2 each bus operation is optimized for each route, according to the previously introduced DP optimization technique. In stage 1.3 the EMS is designed with the ANFIS learning technique, based on the optimal operations. Finally, in stage 1.4 the developed EMS for each bus is implemented. This last stage is the bridge between the *offline optimization and*

Figure 8: Fleet management methodology.

strategy design at vehicle level and the online operation level. At the bus-to-route design design, since in the beginning there is no compiled data, the offline data exploitation and decision making at fleet level is not an input. On the contrary, throughout the bus lifetime this is used as an input for the bus-to-route design stage.

Stage 2: Fleet operation

In this stage, the previously developed EMSs are integrated into each bus, and these are operated in their corresponding lines.

Stage 3: Fleet data exploitation

In stage 3 the obtained data from the fleet operation is processed for the subsequent fleet data analysis.

Based on this analysis, EMS updating and/or *route-to-bus fleet decision making* approach is performed.

Stage 3.1: *Fleet operation data*

In this stage a time period has to be set, with the aim to collect enough data for the processing stage. This watching period, can be set from weeks until years, depending on the data analysis type to be focused on. This stage is the bridge between the *online operation level* and the *offline data exploitation and decision making at fleet level* of the hierarchical decision maker and management for the data acquisition.

Stage 3.2: *Data processing*

The collected data of the previous stage has to be processed, with the aim to get valuable information. The extracted information of the fleet is the SOH of each of the BT, the auxiliary consumption, number of passengers, driving cycle or operation tendencies.

Stage 3.3: *Data analysis*

At this stage an analysis of the whole fleet is performed, with the aim of facilitating the decision making process. At this point, the planned TCO goals fulfillment has to be checked. The first goal of the TCO plan is the fuel consumption limit constrained by the fleet operator. The second goal is the planned buses BT lifetime for the TCO design, that allows to make decisions based on the buses BT lifetime estimation.

Stage 3.4: *Energy management decision making*

Based on the data analysis, in the energy management decision maker stage the new updated EMS design is decided. This stage receives inputs from stage 3.3 and stage 4, with the aim to make decisions for the EMS updates. From stage 3.3 the bus new conditions are updated. From stage 4, based on the fleet management procedure, the new routes re-organization is obtained and the bus re-optimization target is set. The re-optimization target is set based on the final SOC, which is modified and determined with the γ_{BT} constant in Eqs. 6 and 7.

The optimization decisions are made based on the TCO plan, for increasing or decreasing the estimated

buses BT lifetime. On the one hand, in order to increase the BT lifetime of a bus, the BT utilization is decreased, increasing the γ_{BT} and consequently increasing the final SOC target. In case the final SOC matches the initial SOC, the BT utilization is constrained with the ΔSOC_{ref} by means of the w_{SOC} . On the other hand, for the bus BT lifetime to be decreased, decreasing the γ_{BT} BT utilization is harnessed, consequently decreasing the optimization final SOC target. 6.

The decisions made at this stage are the inputs for the *bus-to-route design*, with the aim to re-optimize and re-design the EMS for each bus according to the decisions taken.

Stage 4: Route-to-bus

The *route-to-bus* stage is the stage dealing with the fleet management. It receives inputs from the data processing stage 3.3 and it calculates an output for the stage 3.4 energy management decision making. At this point, it is decided according to the current lifetime of the BTs of the whole fleet and the buses BT lifetime estimation if an EMS update is enough or a re-organization of the fleet is required.

For those routes that require a re-organization, the buses with the best SOH are swapped to the most demanding lines and the buses with the worst SOH are swapped to the least demanding lines. This decision is used as an input for stage 3.4.

5 Results and Analysis

In order to validate the proposed methodology for improving the overall efficiency of the whole fleet a simulation of the fleet presented in Fig. 1 has been performed. With the aim to have a equivalent and referenced auxiliary consumption, 16 kW mean consumption have been considered for all the simulations. For performing the simulations a core i7-6600 CPU with 2.60 GHz and 2.80 GHz with 8 GB of RAM memory computer has been used.

The results presentation is divided into 4 subsections, TCO economic analysis, *bus-to-route* EMS technical analysis, *route-to-bus* decision maker, and *route-to-bus* updated EMS technical analysis. Firstly,

with the aim to validate the fleet level TCO management proposed approach, the TCO economic analysis of the *bus-to-route* EMS designs and *route-to-bus* decision making is presented. Following this, the proposed *bus-to-route* EMS designs are technically evaluated. The *route-to-bus* decision making process based on the buses BT lifetime is explained and technical results are shown. Finally, the *route-to-bus* decisions are technically evaluated in the fourth subsection.

5.1 Total cost of ownership analysis

An economic evaluation has been carried out based on the TCO calculation presented in Subsection 3.1 in order to evaluate the improvements of the proposed approach. This evaluation has been split into two subsections, the *bus-to-route* EMS design evaluation and the *route-to-bus* EMS update.

The developed EMSs have been compared with other EMSs. On the one hand, the *bus-to-route* EMS design has been compared to a charge-depleting charge-sustaining (CDCS) EMS at the beginning of service life of the fleet. The CDCS EMS is commonly used in real application as EMS, known for its low computational effort and low design complexity. The reason for comparing with the CDCS EMS has been to demonstrate the improvement of the bus energy efficiency with the developed fuzzy-logic EMS that has also been validated on a previous work [57] the online implementation.

This comparison allows to evaluate the improvement of the proposed optimized EMS. On the other hand, the *route-to-bus* EMSs update have been compared against the non-updated *bus-to-route* EMS design, with the aim to justify the importance of re-updating the EMS design throughout the bus lifetime based on the buses BT lifetime and TCO.

5.1.1 Bus-to-route energy management strategy design evaluation

The *bus-to-route* evaluation is proceed from the beginning of the fleet lifetime until the SOH evaluation point (further explained in Subsection 5.3). At this point, no BT replacements are required, therefore this price has been excluded, since it is constant for all buses operation. The factors taken into account

have been fuel cost and recharging energy and power costs.

The economic study shows savings comparing the optimized EMS against the CDCS EMS in all the operating buses of the fleet, ranging from 3.95 % until 11.79 %, as shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Total cost of ownership of bus-to-route design and CDCS EMS.

At fleet level the TCO improvement from the beginning of the fleet service life until the SOH evaluation point has been of 7.65 % of TCO improvement. Apart from this, the proposed approach gives the possibility to ensure an EMS that reduces the overall operation costs for the EMS bus-to-route design. This *bus-to-route* approach can be further improved with a regular update, with the aim to learn from the real driving behavior disruptions.

In this work the most valuable information came from the SOH of each of the BTs. However, as it is aforementioned in Section 3.2 Stage 3.2, tendencies data from a real fleet are valuable inputs to further improve the learning process.

5.1.2 Route-to-bus updated energy management strategy evaluation

After evaluating the *bus-to-route* EMS, with the aim to justify the need of updating the EMS, the *route-to-bus* TCO has been evaluated. This TCO evaluation has been made starting from the SOH evaluation point, until the buses BT EOL. For the TCO evaluation of the buses of the whole fleet, the medium BT cost scenario has been applied. After this, the three scenarios have been analyzed for the *route-to-bus* and fleet TCO improvement rate evaluation.

The overall TCO of the buses has been improved from 1.05 % up to 17.71 %, as shown in Fig. 10. However, those buses that have been swapped to the most demanding lines (routes 3 and 4) have increased their own TCO. However, this is compensated with the avoidance of BT replacement on those buses operating in the initial period on the most demanding lines by means of the fleet manager. It is noteworthy the operation modification for buses 7 and 8. In order to reach the service life target, the operation have been changed to operate starting and finishing nearly at the same SOC. This is the reason for having low energy and power costs.

Figure 10: Total cost of ownership of non-updated and updated buses.

For analyzing the range of improvement and justifying the need to swap the buses, an evaluation for the swapped and non-swapped buses has been carried out, as shown in Fig. 11. Further details of the fleet level *route-to-bus* decision maker are described in Subsection 5.3. For this analysis low, medium and high BT cost scenarios have been studied in the 4 buses where swapping has been applied. It is noteworthy that in the three cost scenarios an improvement is achieved, ranging from 1.8% up to 4.28%.

Figure 11: Total cost of ownership evaluation for swapped and non-swapped buses.

Regarding the fleet TCO improvement analysis, the three price scenarios have been evaluated. In the proposed approach the buses BT lifetime requirements and TCO model are achieved. In the low BT price scenario, and improvement of 2.53% has been achieved, for the medium, a 3.88% and for the high BT price scenario a 5.51% at fleet level.

This improvement justifies the need of EMS update and fleet re-organization, with the aim to further improve the TCO of the whole fleet. In addition, the upper fleet level and TCO plan facilitates the decisions when updating the EMS and gives an additional degree of freedom by re-organizing the fleet. Although, the fuel consumption minimization target is an important target, having the TCO picture, gives a clearer and more reliable information in economic terms. It is worth mentioning the case when the BT of a bus arrives to the EOL before the TCO planned years. This will imply an additional economic penalization from the operating company. This penalization has not been taken into account for those buses not reaching the planned buses BT lifetime.

5.2 Bus-to-route energy management strategy technical evaluation

The *bus-to-route* EMS design has been evaluated at the beginning of the fleet lifetime. In Fig. 12 the optimal SOC profiles obtained with the DP are shown, with the respective replication of SOC profiles based on the develop EMS for each route.

Figure 12: Buses SOC operation comparison and RMSEs of optimal and online profiles on the routes.

The developed fuzzy-logic EMSs follow the optimal path with small errors, showing root mean square errors (RMSEs) of up to 0.59 %. This global optimization replication allows to achieve both, fuel consumption minimization and BT aging management.

In Table 3 the obtained technical fuel consumption minimization results are shown. First comparison has been done against DP global optimization, in order to have a benchmark of the routes. The overall errors are low, going from 2.6 % error, up to 6.07 % error. The obtained results with the SOC profile comparison validates the developed EMS for both minimizing fuel and managing BT aging with the SOC profile replication. In addition to this, in order to evaluate the improvement of the proposed optimized EMS design, it has been compared with a charge-depleting charge-sustaining (CDCS) EMS.

In the carried out evaluation, fuel consumption minimization is achieved in all the routes comparing the proposed EMS with the CDCS EMS baseline, ranging from 6.26 % up to 21.61 %. In this way, the *bus-to-route* EMS is technically validated and is proved that substantial fuel savings are achieved. In addition, the achieved results are closer to the DP reference than to the CDCS baseline.

Table 3: Bus-to-route fuel efficiency technical evaluation of the fleet.

Route	Fuel consumption [l/100 km]			DP	CDCS	Route	Fuel consumption [l/100 km]			DP	CDCS
	DP	ANFIS	CDCS	Error [%]	diff. [%]		DP	ANFIS	CDCS	Error [%]	diff. [%]
1	20.30	21.15	23.36	4.19	-9.93	6	19.91	20.43	21.75	2.61	-6.26
2	21.40	22.19	24.61	3.69	-10.34	7	19.34	20.02	21.80	3.52	-8.51
3	36.25	37.28	46.31	2.84	-21.61	8	19.26	19.86	21.72	3.12	-8.95
4	27.22	28.41	33.48	4.37	-16.38	9	22.84	23.62	27.13	3.42	-13.83
5	28.37	29.11	33.80	2.6	-14.91	10	28.98	30.74	35.71	6.07	-14.96

5.3 Route-to-bus decision making based on buses battery lifetime

In this subsection, the lifetime of all the BTs of buses from the whole fleet has been estimated and a bus BT lifetime plan for the whole fleet has been developed. The obtained results are shown in Fig. 13.

After having the buses BT lifetime estimation picture, the SOH evaluation point has been decided. This decision has been taken based on the carried out previous work [20]. The SOH evaluation point has been set around the middle of the half of the BTs EOL (considering 80% as the EOL) for those buses with the minimum BT lifetime estimation. The SOH evaluation point has been set to the year 4 and the

Figure 13: Fleet buses BT SOH evaluation and lifetime estimation.

buses BTs SOH shown in Fig. 13 have been obtained.

Once the SOH evaluation point information is processed, according to the buses service life target and current SOH, decisions are taken. In order to make the most of the BT and avoid replacements, the buses BT lifetime goal has been set to 12 years, which corresponds to the bus service life for the whole fleet.

Based on the *route-to-bus* proposed approach, the routes have been grouped in three classes less demanding, most demanding and average demand. The buses operating in the most demanding routes have been swapped to less demanding lines, and the buses operating in the less demanding routes have been swapped to the most demanding routes. This decision has been made, with the aim to balance the BT lifetime of the buses with the best and the worst SOH.

In Fig. 13 the less demanding, most demanding and average demand routes have been grouped. The less demanding routes match with those routes that have the shortest cycle and daily driven distance and lowest average speed, in this case lines 3 and 4. The shortest cycle distance, shortest daily driven distance and lowest mean speed The most demanding routes are the routes that have the longest cycle and daily distance and higher average speed, identifying routes 7 and 8 in this class and being line 7 the most demanding route. The main reason for this compared to line 8, is the longer cycle length, that

depletes more the BT and consequently degrades more the BT. Finally, the remaining routes that have an average BT degradation, have been grouped in the average demand class. These routes EMS has been updated, however, they do not require routes re-organization for achieving the buses BT lifetime target of 12 years.

In Table 4 the routes re-scheduling is sum-up. Bus number 3 that was operating in line 3 has been swapped to most demanding line. Bus number 7 that was operating in the most demanding route, has been swapped to the less demanding route 3. The same decisions have been applied for the second most and less demanding lines, 4 and 8 respectively. Bus number 4 has been swapped to line 8 and bus number 8 to line 4.

Table 4: Buses and routes swapping.

Group	Bus number	Current line	Swap to line	SOH %
Best SOH	3	3	7	94.96
	4	4	8	94.69
Worst SOH	7	7	3	89.82
	8	8	4	90.19

Once the swap decisions have been made, all the routes are re-optimized with DP and the buses BT lifetimes are estimated, in order to stick to the buses BT lifetime goal. The *route-to-bus* EMS design decision is taken with the aim to meet the predefined BT aging targets and improve the TCO of the whole fleet.

5.4 Route-to-bus strategy update technical analysis

Based on the decision making, all the EMSs of the fleet are updated. For this long term *route-to-bus* EMS update, two separate analyses have been carried out. Firstly, the technical fuel consumption analysis of the whole fleet and secondly by the buses BT lifetime study of the whole fleet.

The objective of this analysis is to remark the importance of updating the EMS with the DP optimization, with the aim to make the most of the proposed hierarchical EMS. Therefore, the updated EMS and the non-updated results have been technically compared.

5.4.1 Fuel consumption impact

The evaluation in terms of fuel consumption is shown in Table 5. The overall tendency of the obtained results, has been an increase on fuel consumption up to 78.89 % and 51.24 % for the routes re-scheduled from the most demanding to the less demanding lines. It is noteworthy that the highest fuel consumption decrease also matches with the buses swapped to the less demanding routes, decreasing up to 44.98% of fuel consumption. In spite of the obtained results in terms of fuel consumption, in Subsection 5.1.2 TCO improvement is shown.

Table 5: Fuel efficiency technical evaluation of the fleet.

Buses	Fuel consumption [l/100 km]			DP	Non-
	Non-update	DP	Updated	Error	updated
	EMS	Re-optimization	EMS	[%]	diff. [%]
1	22.47	22.27	23.86	7.14	+6.18
2	23.82	27.32	28.47	4.21	+17.79
3	39.43	23.82	24.95	4.74	-44.98
4	29.75	23.46	24.52	4.52	-19.27
5	31.01	29.29	31.12	6.56	+0.35
6	22.05	24.85	26.05	4.83	+27.09
7	21.70	48.6	49.97	2.82	+78.89
8	21.5	35.14	36.31	3.33	+51.24
9	25.22	25.73	27.34	6.26	+8.07
10	32.38	26.77	29.75	11.13	-8.47

5.4.2 Battery lifetime impact

Starting from the SOH evaluation point until the end of fleet service life, the applied updated EMS behavior have been studied. The obtained results are shown in Table 6. The overall buses BT lifetime of the fleet has been increased up to 45.21 %. However, 2 buses BT lifetime has been reduced. As it is aforementioned, the main goal of the proposed approach is to optimize the TCO. For optimizing the TCO, BT lifetime is managed to meet the buses BT lifetime objective. In the case of these 2 buses (3 and 4), in the SOH evaluation point, the BT lifetime was above the other buses. With the aim to further improve the TCO, the fuel consumption of these buses has been reduced, as shown in Table 5, and the BT lifetime has been decreased.

Focusing on the 12 years buses service, on the one hand, with the updated EMSs, all the buses met the requirement. On the other hand, with the non-updated EMSs, only buses 3, 4, 5 and 10 met the goal. These buses again match with the buses with the fuel consumption reduction. To sum up, the non-updated EMS have random results, as it was initially designed for some specific conditions, changing throughout the bus lifetime. Therefore, for ensuring the BT management, the EMS needs to be updated.

Table 6: Fleet buses BT aging technical evaluation of the fleet.

Buses	BT lifetime [years]		Non-updated diff. [%]	Buses	BT lifetime [years]		Non-updated diff. [%]
	Non-update	Updated			Non-update	Updated	
	EMS	EMS			EMS	EMS	
1	11.49	12.61	+9.29	6	9.92	12.24	+20.94
2	9.86	12.73	+25.41	7	7.67	12.15	+45.21
3	14.59	12.56	-14.95	8	7.91	12.15	+42.27
4	13.77	12.47	-9.91	9	11.07	12.28	+10.36
5	12.19	12.24	+0.41	10	12.25	12.22	-0.25

6 Conclusions

In this paper a hierarchical energy management strategy design methodology for total cost of ownership management at fleet level is proposed. The proposed approach is based on a hierarchical decision maker and management composed of three levels. In the inner part, a fuzzy-logic based EMS is implemented to manage the online operation. To reduce the EMS design complexity, at the online operation upper level, the fuzzy-logic design has been automatized offline. This automation is based on a dynamic programming optimization and a neuro-fuzzy learning technique. Finally, the outer part is the offline data exploitation and decision maker, aiming to establish the dynamic programming optimization design. The fleet has been re-organized and the online operation energy management strategy is updated throughout the bus lifetime. These decisions are made based on the evaluated BT lifetime of the fleet, with the aim to meet the planned total cost of ownership requirements. The main findings have been summarized as follows.

- ***Bus-to-route* vehicle level management** : The proposed *bus-to-route* approach that performs the improvement of the local efficiency of each bus composing the fleet, have shown improvements in both technical and economic aspects. The obtained results in terms of total cost of ownership at fleet level show a substantial improvement of 7.65 % against a charge-sustaining charge-depleting strategy. Regarding the technical aspect, fuel efficiency improvements ranging from 6.26-21.61 % compared to a charge-depleting charge-sustaining strategy have been obtained.
- ***Route-to-bus* fleet re-organization** : The *route-to-bus* fleet re-organization, targeting to balance the battery lifetimes, has been evaluated isolating the buses that have been re-schedule. Three battery price scenarios have been defined, with the aim to analyze different future scenarios. In the low medium and high battery price scenarios improvements of 1.8 %, 2.9 % and 4.28 % have been achieved.
- ***Route-to-bus* fleet buses energy management strategy update** : The fleet total cost of own-

ership has been improved a 5.51 % compared with not updating the buses energy management strategies. When managing a fleet of vehicles, not only the fuel consumption minimization is a key factor, but the whole total cost of ownership improvement. Managing and sticking to the developed total cost of ownership plan, will allow to increase the fleet operation savings. In addition, the upper fleet level point of view and TCO plan facilitates the decisions when updating the EMS and gives an additional degree of freedom of managing the fleet.

Our future work and research will be focused on the hardware-in-the-loop implementation and testing for the oncoming real fleet implementation.

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